

PRN dosing

PRN stands for *pro re nata*, which translates into “as the situation arises” when used as an idiom, contrasts with regular usage and emphasises situational use only – when the need arises. It assumes significance when prescribing morphine in the setting of cancer pain; a shift from PRN q 2 hourly dosing to PRN q 4 hourly dosing might mark a shift from the acute phase of opioid titration to the opioid tolerant phase and likely attainment of stable pain control.

Pain score threshold, frequency of use of rescue medication, stable analgesic dose for baseline pain for 48-72 hours and favourable functional status have been used as operational indicators to define stable pain control in the context of cancer pain- related clinical trials.

This term is not to be used in the context of anticipatory prescribing at the end of life.

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